

Xenon Effects during Power Transient of a Heat-Pipe Cooled Microreactor using the DireWolf Code Suite

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates xenon effects during power transients in a heat-pipe cooled microreactor using the multiphysics DireWolf code suite. Xenon transients significantly influence reactivity and thermal behavior, impacting performance and safety margins in microreactors with passive control systems. In this paper, two modeling approaches were evaluated: a diffusion-based method and a reduced-order point kinetics (PKE) method. Both approaches were implemented within DireWolf, which couples Griffin for neutronics and Bison for thermal analysis, along with the MOOSE Thermal Hydraulic Module for simulating primary heat exchanger airflow. A representative long-transient scenario was simulated by varying heat-pipe mass flow rates to induce power ramp-up and ramp-down conditions within 140 hours. Results show that xenon concentration initially decreases during power increase due to higher burnup, then rises to a new equilibrium, with the opposite trend observed during power reduction. Two xenon modeling assumptions were compared: tracking xenon dynamically versus assuming equilibrium xenon concentration. The equilibrium assumption produced conservative temperature predictions, up to 20°C higher than xenon tracking, making it useful for bounding analyses. While the diffusion method accurately captured spatial feedback and xenon worth, it required approximately 52 days of high-performance computing time. Conversely, the PKE method completed the same analysis in 8 days, albeit with slight overprediction of power and temperature. Both methods exhibited consistent trends, confirming PKE as a practical option for rapid evaluations and design iterations, while diffusion remains critical for detailed validation. These findings highlight the trade-off between computational cost, fidelity, and xenon modeling assumptions in microreactor transient analysis.

Keywords: xenon-effect, power-transients, heat-pipe, microreactor, DireWolf

1. INTRODUCTION

Microreactors are emerging as a viable solution for delivering reliable, resilient, decentralized and scalable power. These reactors are designed to be compact, rapidly deployed and operate autonomously allowing them to be uniquely suited for applications where traditional energy infrastructure is impractical or vulnerable. Particularly, microreactors can offer energy security and sustainability in various applications such as offering power to isolated communities, and remote military installations, enabling long-duration space missions and exploration, and supporting critical infrastructure such as hospitals, schools and data centers or during disaster relief operations.

As grids increasingly integrate various energy sources, such as renewables, fossil fuels and nuclear energy, there is an increased interest in operating nuclear reactors in a load-following manner, ramping power output up or down depending on the power needs and grids resources availability. This operational paradigm introduces more frequent and pronounced power transients, which in turn amplify the importance of understanding in detail the dynamic reactivity effects such as xenon poisoning. Xenon transients can impact performance, restartability and safety margins, especially for

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reactor designs with control systems that are passive or simplified like in heat-pipe cooled microreactors.

This paper investigates the temporal evolution of xenon and iodine concentration during a mock but representative power transient scenario in a heat-pipe cooled microreactor, with the goal of understanding reactor core behavior during this transient and informing the safety analysis and design approach that can enhance the reactor safety, resilience and performance. A multiphysics approach is undertaken using the finite-element MOOSE [1] code suite DireWolf [2], developed by Idaho National Laboratory (INL). Previous work has shown the capability of DireWolf to model steady-state and design basis transients including reactivity insertion, overcooling, loss of cooling and heat-pipe failure transients [3-5]. DireWolf utilized Griffin [6] for the neutronics analysis and Bison [7] for the thermal analysis. In this case, the power transient is simulated by altering the mass-flow rate which can in turn lead to an increase or decrease of the power level of the reactor core. This paper includes a brief description of the reactor design examined and the methodology followed for this analysis, including the neutronics and thermal mesh generation, the cross-section generation using the Monte Carlo code Serpent 2 [8] and the DireWolf models developed. The power and temperature levels resulting from the power transient cases are presented for two distinct simulations, allowing xenon tracking, and assuming equilibrium xenon and for two different approaches in DireWolf, using diffusion and point kinetics neutronics solvers.

2. MICROREACTOR MODEL & METHODOLOGY

To simulate xenon behavior during a power transient in a computationally efficient manner, the modeling framework within DireWolf employs two approaches: a diffusion-based method for spatially resolved analysis and a point kinetics model for a rapid, reactor-level lumped evaluation. Central to the DireWolf models developed is the core mesh, which defines the spatial discretization of the reactor geometry for the neutronics and thermal solution. In addition to the mesh, accurate simulation demands a well-characterized nuclear data set, provided in the form of a multigroup cross-section library tailored to the reactor operating conditions. This section describes briefly the microreactor core design, the mesh generation, the methodology used to produce the cross-section library utilizing the Monte Carlo code Serpent 2 and the DireWolf methodology, and the input model development.

2.1. Core Design

The microreactor examined in this paper is designed to operate at 2-3MWth at full power. The reactor core is made of graphite core blocks with channels for heat-pipes and fuel, and a graphite central reflector. The reactor uses 19.75 wt% High-Assay Low-Enriched Uranium (HALEU) oxycarbide fuel in the form of TRi-structural ISOtropic (TRISO) fuel particles that are encapsulated within a graphite matrix forming fuel compacts. Heat is removed from the reactor core and transferred to the power conversion system (PCS) using heat pipes. Figure 1 shows the core geometry.

Figure 1. Microreactor Core Layout.

2.2. Mesh Generation

DireWolf relies on finite-element methods, which require a spatial mesh to represent the reactor core. Depending on the physics being modeled, different mesh resolutions can be used. For this analysis, a 3D assembly-homogenized mesh was employed for the neutronics simulation in Griffin, while a 3D pin-resolved heterogeneous mesh was used for the thermal modeling in Bison, as shown in Figure 2. The Griffin neutronics mesh was generated using the Neutronics Enhanced Mesh Operations (NEMO) [9] tool developed by INL while the Bison thermal 2D mesh was generated within NEMO and was extruded to 3D using the MOOSE mesh capabilities, enabling consistent geometry representation across physics domains.

Figure 2. Assembly homogenized 3D Griffin neutronic mesh (left) & Pin resolved 3D Bison thermal mesh (right).

2.3. Cross-section Generation

The Griffin neutronics steady-state and transient solvers require neutron cross-section data that are resolved by energy group. These multigroup macroscopic cross-sections were parameterized at key state variables such as the reactor core component temperatures and control drum positions, forming a structured evaluation matrix covering the range of conditions for the reactor's normal operation, anticipated transients, and postulated accidents.

For this analysis, the following parameters were defined: fuel temperatures ranging from 27°C to 1227°C, moderator temperatures between 27°C and 1227°C, reflector temperatures between 27°C and 927°C, and several positions for intact and inadvertently rotating control drums ranging from 0° to 180°. To reduce the number of matrix state points, a feature in the DireWolf suite was used to exclude non-physical configurations, resulting in a total of 1666 evaluation state points.

An 11-group energy structure was employed for the cross-section generation [3]. The cross-section data was produced using the Monte Carlo code Serpent 2 version 2.2.1, utilizing the ENDF/B.VII.1 [7] nuclear data library. The Serpent 2 model used, reflects the core design specifications, and was updated to include equilibrium concentrations of key fission product poisons such as xenon, using the "set xenon 1" card. In addition, the fission yields of the poisons ^{135}Xe , ^{135}I , ^{149}Pm and ^{149}Sm , along with their homogenized microscopic cross-section in each fuel flake and atomic densities are calculated by Serpent 2, together with the macroscopic, homogenized nodal cross-sections for each state point required by the Griffin solver. Utilizing the Griffin ISOXML module, two separate cross-sections libraries are

created, one assuming equilibrium xenon, and a second one which contains the homogenized microscopic poison cross-sections of ^{135}Xe , ^{135}I , ^{149}Pm and ^{149}Sm .

With the cross-section data and neutronics mesh prepared, standalone Griffin simulations using the Continuous Finite Element Method for Diffusion (CFEM-Diffusion) were performed to compute the Super Homogenization (SPH) [11, 12] factors for each state point in the evaluation matrix of the cross-section library generated. The SPH method was applied to correct the errors introduced by the coarse, assembly-homogenized mesh and the diffusion approximation. The SPH factors are spatially limited to the fuel regions in this analysis. Verification of the generated cross-section and SPH factors was conducted by comparing Griffin-calculated eigenvalues to those obtained from Serpent 2 for each evaluation point. Previous work has shown that when there is no xenon tracking the eigenvalue discrepancies are less than 0.5 pcm, confirming the accuracy of the cross-section data generated for the homogenization scheme [3]. In this study, with xenon tracking, the eigenvalue discrepancies were found to be on an average less than 56 pcm. The larger discrepancies found can be attributed to the differences between Serpent results with equilibrium xenon and the Griffin calculated xenon contribution based on the power level.

2.4. DireWolf Methodology

The DireWolf suite supports multiple approaches for modeling fission product poison concentrations, particularly xenon, which plays a critical role in reactor kinetics and reactivity feedback. Two methodologies are evaluated in this analysis: one based on diffusion calculation and another leveraging point kinetics equations for faster evaluation.

The diffusion approach utilizes Griffin's PJFNK solver in the transient executioner to solve the neutron transport equations in full spatial detail and treat the time independent variable. The density of the ^{135}Xe isotope and its significant daughter isotopes involved in reactor poisoning are calculated by Griffin. This method accounts for the spatial distribution of neutron flux and material properties. It is tightly integrated with the SPH-corrected cross-section library and is particularly suited for detailed transient and steady-state analyses. However, it is computationally expensive, especially when evaluating long transients. Despite its cost, the diffusion-based method provides accurate xenon concentration profiles that reflect spatial feedback effects.

To address the computational limitations of the diffusion approach, another approach was also implemented in DireWolf, applying microscopic depletion for xenon buildup using point-kinetics, *PKE*. This method simplifies the reactor model by assuming spatially averaged parameters and solving time-dependent equations for neutron population and xenon buildup. The point kinetics approach is significantly faster, enabling rapid estimation of xenon concentrations across a wide range of operating conditions. While this method sacrifices some accuracy due to its assumption of uniform flux and temperature distributions across the core, it allows for faster evaluations of the results which are particularly suitable for screening studies and scoping analyses in early design phases, especially when simulating long transients.

3. ANALYSIS & RESULTS

This study conducted a coupled neutronic and thermal analysis of the heat pipe microreactor using the DireWolf suite. The workflow begins with Griffin, which computes the neutronic solution (flux and power distribution), based on user-defined initial temperature conditions. The resulting assembly unit cell power at each axial node is then apportioned uniformly among the fuel channels within the unit cell in Bison, which calculates the full 3D temperature distribution of the reactor core. The reactor core thermal model is integrated with the Primary Heat Exchanger (PHX) air flow and heat transfer models to capture the effects of air inlet flow and temperature distribution across individual heat pipe cooling channels. Each channel is represented by a 1-D air flow model implemented using the MOOSE Thermal Hydraulic Module (THM) within the MOOSE framework. Multiple instances of this 1-D air flow model (one per heat pipe) are coupled to Bison, enabling detailed thermal interaction between the heat pipes and the air-cooling system.

3.1. Power Transient

To perform the power transients that will evaluate the xenon behavior, several steps were completed prior to the transient. First a criticality drum search calculation evaluated the critical drum positions, then a steady-state calculation was performed evaluating the steady-state flux and temperatures and this calculation was followed by an adjoint calculation to calculate the reactivity change. A null transient was also executed to ensure that the converged steady-state solution did not change with the transient solution scheme in the absence of any perturbation.

The transient calculations were restarted from the converged steady-state full power (2MWth) conditions including power and temperature distributions and the critical drum position. To simulate the power transients, at $t = 0$ seconds, the cooling air mass flow rate corresponding to each heat-pipe in the secondary side was increased to achieve a new power level that is approximately two times the power level during the steady-state calculation. After the initial increase, the mass flow rate remained constant for 216000 seconds (60 hours) until a new equilibrium state was reached. At time $t = 216000.01$ seconds in the transient the mass flow rate was decreased to immediately reduce the power level to be approximately half. Subsequently, the calculation continued for another 288000 seconds (80 hours) maintaining the same mass flow rate. These changes in the cooling air mass flow rate drove the temperature changes of the core components, which led to power increase and decrease. Note that the power transient simulated in this analysis doesn't necessarily represent a realistic load-following scenario, instead it was modeled to demonstrate the fission poison (Xenon and Iodine) transient behavior.

As mentioned above, the power transient was performed for two distinct cases, tracking xenon to evaluate the poison effects and not tracking xenon, assuming equilibrium concentration. The power transient was also performed utilizing two different neutronics methods within Griffin, diffusion with a functionality to calculate the density of ^{135}Xe and the isotopes in its decay chain and point kinetics (PKE) employing microscopic depletion for xenon buildup and accounting for Xenon reactivity feedback. The power levels during this transient with the normalized xenon and iodine nuclide concentrations (using diffusion & PKE) are shown in Figure 3. During this power transient, as the power increases, xenon concentration initially decreases because the burnup is increased due to a higher reaction rate. The xenon concentration reaches a minimum in about 0.75 hours and then starts to increase and reaches a new equilibrium, at the new equilibrium power at about 52 hours. Once the power ramps down, the opposite effect occurs, where the xenon concentration reaches a maximum in about 1.46 hours after the power ramp down is initiated, and then starts to decrease reaching a new equilibrium at the new equilibrium power level at about 59.9 hours after the power ramp down is initiated. As seen in Figure 3, the PKE method overpredicts the power levels both in the case of xenon tracking and equilibrium xenon, although starting from the same steady-state value and assuming the same mass flow rate, which can be attributed to the uniform values that are used in this lower-fidelity method. This overprediction in power results in a slight overprediction in the iodine and xenon number densities, however the general trends are very similar.

Figure 4 and Figure 5 show the average and maximum fuel and heat-pipe temperatures respectively for the two cases: assuming xenon tracking and equilibrium xenon, and for the diffusion and PKE methods. For this power transient, when fuel and heat-pipe temperatures decrease due to the increased cooling air mass flow rate, the power ramps up due to the negative reactivity temperature coefficients. On the contrary, when a lower mass flow rate of the cooling air is applied, the heat-pipe and fuel temperatures increase which lead to a decrease in power again due to the negative reactivity temperature coefficients. Similar to the xenon and iodine concentrations, the PKE method overpredicts the temperature when there is xenon tracking on, and there is a nontrivial difference in the results up to 15 degrees, although the general trends are similar. The temperatures seem to have a significantly better agreement between the diffusion and the PKE method when equilibrium xenon is assumed. It is important to note here that when equilibrium xenon is assumed the temperature are predicted at a higher state than when xenon tracking is applied. The difference between the equilibrium xenon prediction and the xenon tracking prediction is marginal, with values larger than 20 degrees. This confirms that performing a calculation with equilibrium xenon could provide a conservative result with higher fuel temperature. Figure 6 shows the xenon worth in relation to the power transient. In this case the xenon worth is not larger than 836 pcm.

Figure 3. ^{135}I and ^{135}Xe normalized number densities and power levels for the diffusion and PKE during a power transient.

Figure 4. Fuel average (left) and fuel maximum (right) ΔT and power levels for the diffusion and PKE method during a power transient assuming xenon tracking and equilibrium xenon.

Figure 5. Heat-pipe average (left) and heat-pipe maximum (right) ΔT and power levels for the diffusion and PKE method during a power transient assuming xenon tracking and equilibrium xenon.

Figure 6. Xenon worth and power levels for the diffusion method during a power transient assuming xenon tracking and equilibrium xenon.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study developed a DireWolf multiphysics model to analyze the xenon behavior during a long power transient in a heat-pipe cooled microreactor using the DireWolf multiphysics code suite. Two neutronics approaches were compared: a diffusion-based method and a reduced-order point kinetics (PKE) method. Both approaches captured the expected xenon and iodine dynamics during power ramp-up and ramp-down: xenon concentration initially decreases following a power increase due to enhanced burnup, then rises to a new equilibrium after approximately 50 hours; conversely, xenon peaks shortly after power reduction before stabilizing at a lower level. These trends are consistent with classical xenon transients observed in light-water reactors, although the magnitude of xenon worth in the microreactor is significantly smaller and the concentration changes are less pronounced due to the reactor's low power level and compact size.

The comparison of the results between xenon tracking and the equilibrium xenon assumption revealed that equilibrium xenon assumption could lead to higher temperature predictions, up to 20°C, making it potentially suitable for bounding analyses. In terms of computational performance, for this long power transient that lasted in total 140 hours (504,000 seconds), smaller time steps were required when the mass-flow rate increased or decreased to reach the new power levels, while larger time steps were taken once the calculations were stabilized. In the case of the diffusion method the maximum allowable time step was found to be 25 seconds to avoid unstable numeric behavior while the smallest time step used was 0.01 seconds, resulting in a total of 20,231 individual time steps. In the case of the PKE method, larger time steps were allowed to reach a fully converged solution, with the smallest time step used being 0.01 seconds and the largest time step being 60 seconds, resulting in a total of 11,850 individual time steps. Using 64 cores with these time steps, the diffusion approach required 52 days for xenon tracking and 20 days for equilibrium xenon, while the PKE method completed the same cases in 8 days and 5.5 days, respectively. This represents a substantial reduction in runtime, making PKE highly attractive for design iterations and preliminary safety evaluations, while diffusion remains essential for final validation and spatially resolved feedback analysis.

Overall, these findings highlight the trade-offs between the fidelity and computational cost associated with the modeling assumptions. Based on this study, xenon effects, while present, do not challenge the safety margins related to the high temperature limits of the core components for the examined power transient scenarios. Future work should include more realistic or extended power transient cases, and optimization in the convergence criteria and solvers that will allow larger time steps and thus faster calculations while ensuring accurate results.

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